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Working Paper

A METHODOLOGICAL INQUIRY INTO THE DATA GENERATING PROCESS CONCERNING NEW JOBS AND SKILLS

Methodology

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Abstract

In this paper, we put to the test two innovative approaches, which are both based on web data, to examine occupations and skills. Driven by technological change, new tasks, occupations and skills have emerged whereas others have become redundant. At the same time, existing occupations have substantially transformed. These transformations have been studied from the academic and policy perspectives, often on the basis of data collected from interviews, surveys, trade publications, job advertisements and existing occupational or skill classifications. The traditional methods and data sources, however, have been criticised for several reasons. Many have suggested that they are not suitable to identify new occupations and skills because data are usually lagged. This complicates the identification of new occupations and skills, and makes it very difficult to respond to current trends in a timely manner.

Web data are an interesting tool to overcome these issues and are, therefore, at the heart of our report, which is methodological in nature. More specifically, we test two ways of identifying new occupations and skills in six case studies. The first method is based on a set of *job advertisements published online*. Vacancies are detailed and contain information about education, skill and other requirements. Moreover, by considering for which positions job vacancies are published, we can find new occupations. The second method relies on the *meta-data and other information available on online job boards*. By examining the occupational structure and tags used, one can get insights into upcoming or new occupations and skills. In this report, we show that both methodologies can be used to study occupations and skills and explain what their advantages and limitations are. By piloting easy-to-use and up-to-date methodologies to analyse new occupations and skills in real time, we aspire to provide valuable inputs for policy-makers, education institutes and other stakeholders.

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1. Introduction

In the last few decades, the impact of technological change on Europe's labour markets has been widely studied and discussed. Numerous contributions of an academic, policy and popular nature have debated the future of work, asking how technological progress affects employment opportunities, working conditions, skill demand, wages and other factors. Technological change shapes occupations, skills and tasks. New occupations and skills emerge while others become obsolete. Yet, these dynamics are not new, nor is the interest in them and the debate about them.

Many efforts in the literature have, therefore, been devoted to the identification of new occupations and skills. Traditionally, new occupations and skills have been identified on the basis of existing classifications, trade publications, employer surveys, interviews and other sources. These traditional sources and methods, however, have been challenged in a number of recent studies (e.g. by Beblavý *et al.*, 2016a). Well-known issues are that the traditional data sources are often lagged, incomplete and of a low quality, making them less suitable for the identification of new occupations and skills, especially in real time.

Internet data can serve as a way to address some of these issues. The use of web data in the social sciences is rapidly advancing and there are many studies that focus specifically on labour-related issues. Nevertheless, only a handful of contributions have examined how Internet data can be used to identify new occupations and skills. Nevertheless, web data have a great potential to serve as a data source for this purpose. Some key advantages are the real-time data availability, the large and diverse samples and the straightforward data collection process. Web data can be extracted from many sources, such as online job portals, social networks or surveys. In this report, we focus on online job boards and their vacancies and put to the test innovative methods to detect new occupations and skills.

To this end, the report presents a series of case studies that are based on two distinct strategies. The first strategy is to identify new occupations and skills by analysing the job advertisements published online (through a semantic analysis). A careful analysis of job titles, descriptions, tasks and responsibilities, requirements and other conditions can be very revealing. This strategy provides a great level of detail, but semantic analysis is not always easy to perform. The second strategy involves identifying new occupations and skills on the basis of the meta-data available on job boards (i.e. the 'tag' system and the occupational structure that the portals use). New occupations and skills are found when new tags are added to the job portal. This strategy is very easy to carry out but offers less information. In this report, we show that both strategies are viable and facilitate research into new occupations and skills.

The focus of this paper is on the methodological process and the data source used, and only to a lesser extent on the findings obtained. It is a deliverable for Work Package 21 of the InGRID project (Task 21.1.2, MS97). The findings will be explored in more depth in our taxonomy report, which constitutes another deliverable for the same work package. It is, therefore, important to explain how these reports are linked. Figure 1.1 shows a typical research set-up and illustrates how our approach differs. A research paper is generally composed of an introduction and literature review, a description of the methodology and data set used, a discussion of the results and a conclusions. Our work for Work Package 21 differs from this traditional structure, in the sense that we produce three reports (all are based on the same set of underlying research papers that we prepared): a state of the art report, which thoroughly reviews the academic and policy literature, a methodological report, which zooms

in on traditional and more innovative methods and data sources, and a taxonomy report, which presents the results obtained by using these methods and data and draws conclusions. We therefore recommend readers to also take a look at these two other reports when going through this methodological paper. We decided to go for this approach as this allows us to better understand each of these three dimensions and to devote to each of them a sufficient discussion.

Figure 1.1 Typical research set-up and how our approach differs

The remainder of this report is, therefore, structured as follows. Section 2 briefly recalls the traditional approach that is commonly used to identify new occupations and skills in the academic and policy literature. In Section 3, innovative approaches to identify new occupations and skills are introduced. These approaches are embedded in a rapidly advancing field which makes use of Internet data to study labour market-related issues. Section 3 further reviews the most recent literature on the topic. Both of these sections build on previous work by Beblavý *et al.* (2016a) and Lenaerts *et al.* (2016). Section 4 constitutes the core of this report, as it aims to test some of these innovative methods. To achieve this goal, the section presents a series of case studies that have been performed in light of the InGRID project. Three of these case studies use a dataset of vacancies published online while two case studies use the meta-data available on the job portal instead (i.e. the occupational structure that job portals use to cluster job vacancies and the closely related ‘tag’ system). The final case study is cross-cutting. Some of these case studies are described in more detail in Tijdens *et al.* (2015), Beblavý *et al.* (2016b), Beblavý *et al.* (2016c) and Beblavý *et al.* (2016d). In Section 5, the main findings of the study are summarised.

2. Identifying new jobs and skills: the traditional approach in the academic and policy literature

In the academic and policy literature, the impact of technological change on the labour market has been examined from several perspectives. One of those perspectives is that of occupations and skills. As a result of technological progress, existing occupations have radically changed, new occupations have emerged and other occupations have become obsolete. Similarly, new skills have been introduced while other skills are no longer demanded in the labour market. These dynamics have been recorded at different stages all throughout history. An interesting example is presented by Chin *et al.* (2006), who study the impact of the adoption of steam engines in the merchant industry in the 19th century. As ships were equipped with steam engines instead of sails, the occupation of engineer - which was new at the time - became much more important. On the other hand, the occupation of sail-maker became redundant and medium-skilled seamen were replaced by low-skilled engine room operators.

Previous research on the effects of technological progress on occupations and skills has relied on a number of methods and data sources to identify new occupations and skills. Crosby (2002) explains that technological progress affects the tasks that employers want their workers to carry out. At first, these new tasks may become part of occupations that already exist (*evolving occupation*). When this is not possible (e.g. because the task is too different from the other tasks that the worker has) or when the new task dominates the other tasks (e.g. it becomes the worker's main task), a *new occupation* emerges (which is defined as an occupation that only recently materialised). Crosby (2002) further refers to new occupations with low employment counts that are expected to gain importance as *emerging occupations*. New tasks are typically associated with new skills and changes in the skill demand. In order to identify new occupations and the underlying new tasks and skills, one has to know which occupations already existed before and which did not.

How can this be achieved? According to Crosby (2002), new occupations and skills are generally defined on the basis of surveys (e.g. asking employers to list new occupations), interviews, trade publications, job advertisements, case studies, and occupational/skills classifications (i.e. new occupations are those that have not yet been added to the most recent edition). Often, several of these data sources are combined. The Texas Career Development Resources Office, for example, uses employer surveys, trade publications, vacancies and the 1980 Standard Occupational Classification System (SOC).¹ Similarly, the US Bureau of Labor conducts employer surveys and a census. In the academic literature, most emphasis is on occupational and skill classifications, such as the ILO's ISCO and ISCED, and the EU's ESCO (see ILO, 2015). The main issue associated with such classifications, however, is that generally these are updated very rarely.² This raises the question whether these classifications are sufficiently up-to-date and whether it is meaningful to identify an occupation as 'new' because it is not included in the most recent classification. Especially in sectors and firms that are rapidly progressing, this is problematic.

Traditional data sources³ generally are well-structured, representative, accurate, and complete. Data, however, often are only available with a lag. In addition, in some cases, data are frequently revised,

1 An interesting contribution on occupational classifications and their revisions is Herman & Abraham (1999).

2 ISCO was released/updated in 1958, 1968, 1988 and 2008; ISCED in 1976, 1997 and 2011.

3 Throughout this report, 'traditional data sources and methods' refers to (labour force) surveys, census data, interviews, trade publications, etc., i.e. the data sources summed up in this section.

sample sizes are small, and data quality may be low (Wright, 2012; Shapiro, 2014). For these reasons, traditional data sources prove to be less suitable to identify new occupations and skills (as real-time information is essential, see Damarin (2006)).

In response to these concerns, researchers have strived to develop new methods and find alternative data sources. Many have turned to the Internet, which can serve both as a research platform and a source of real-time labour market data. We also start from the idea of using Internet data and examine how such data can be used to analyse new occupations and skills. There have been several other applications in which web data are used to study economic and social phenomena, but only very few have focused on occupations and skills and on new occupations and skills, in particular. Our contribution is, therefore, innovative, as it puts some of these methods and data sources to the test.

3. Innovative methodologies to identify new jobs and skills: previous research

In order to overcome the limitations of traditional datasets, researchers have extended their work to other data sources including web data.⁴ Web data have become increasingly widespread in the social sciences in the last two decades, as the Internet developed into a research platform and a data source (Kuhn & Skuterud, 2004; Benfield & Szlemko, 2006; Askitas & Zimmermann, 2009; 2015; and D'Amuri & Marcucci, 2010). Web data are available in real time and, therefore, allow to capture current trends. This is an essential feature if one wants to identify new occupations and skills as they arise. *Real-time labour market data* can be obtained from job boards, social networks and many other websites (Dorrer *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, the rise of the Internet has considerably affected many labour-related process, such as job search, recruitment and matching with far-reaching consequences for job seekers, employees, employers, recruitment agencies, education institutes and other stakeholders (Dorrer *et al.*, 2012; Carnevale *et al.*, 2014; Kuhn, 2014; Kuhn & Mansour, 2014; Askitas & Zimmermann, 2015).

3.1 What web-based data sources are available?

We consider four potential data sources: online job portals and other labour market intermediaries, social networks, web surveys and Google Trends.

Online job portals and other labour market intermediaries

Job portals and labour market intermediaries connect labour demand and supply, which makes them a particularly interesting data source for research (Carnevale *et al.*, 2014; Kuhn, 2014; Kuhn & Mansour, 2014; Kureková *et al.*, 2015). Detailed data can be derived in several ways: from the vacancies and CVs published on the job board or intermediary platform, from how vacancies and other data are structured on the portal or platform, and from any other information available (e.g. employer reviews, career advice, data on wages and working hours, etc.). Many job boards have developed into career community websites, targeting employers, employees, job seekers and career counsellors. Similarly, online intermediaries often are rich information sources. Both job portals and intermediaries provide a lot of information, which generally also is fairly detailed. Web data are typically combined with data from traditional sources.

Research & Examples: earlier work has mostly used data obtained from private online job boards (see Capiluppi & Baravalle, 2010; Štefánik, 2012; Kuhn & Shen, 2013). One notable exception is the paper by Kureková *et al.* (2015a), who perform a cross-country analysis of employers' demand for skills in the Czech Republic, Denmark and Ireland using EURES data.

Researchers have studied - on the basis of vacancies or CVs - mobility (Cañibano *et al.*, 2008; Masso *et al.*, 2011; Masso *et al.*, 2013), discrimination (Maurer-Fazio, 2012; Kuhn & Shen, 2013; Maurer-Fazio & Lei, 2015), over-qualification of job applicants (Shen & Kuhn, 2013), job search behaviour (Kudlyak *et al.*, 2012; Faberman & Kudlyak, 2014), mismatch (Capiluppi & Baravalle, 2010; Marinescu, 2015), unemployment insurance (Marinescu & Rathelot, 2015), skill requirements (Kennan *et al.*, 2009; Huang *et al.*, 2009; Kureková *et al.*, 2012; Sasser Modestino *et al.*, 2014; Hershbein & Kahn, 2015) and several other topics. This literature is closely related to studies that use printed job advertisements (Jackson *et al.*, 2005; Jackson, 2007; Dörfler & van de Werfhorst, 2009; Barnichon, 2010).

⁴ Throughout this report, web data and Internet data are used as synonyms.

The bulk of work on online intermediaries has focused on MTurk and UpWork, i.e. very large online platforms. Examples are the studies by Buhrmester *et al.* (2011), Horton (2011), Horton *et al.* (2011), Ghani *et al.* (2014) and Pallais (2014). Other work has investigated smaller platforms, such as CoContest (Maselli & Fabo, 2015) and AlmaLaurea (Bagues & Labini, 2009). Online intermediaries and platforms have also been increasingly used to carry out experiments (see Pallais, 2014; Pallais & Sands, forthcoming, and Horton, forthcoming). Besides intermediaries, TESS (Time-sharing Experiments for the Social Sciences) is an online platform for experiments (using a representative sample of US-based adults).

Job portals:

- Public: EURES (the European Union's mobility portal), websites of public employment services
- Private: Monster, Stepstone, Careerbuilder, Indeed

Intermediaries: UpWork, TaskRabbit, AlmaLaurea, Amazon Mechanical Turk, CoContest

Social networks

Social networks present an interesting but underexploited data source to study the labour market. These networks can play a major role because they can reduce search frictions. Jobs are increasingly advertised on Facebook and Twitter. Job applicants and employees typically have a LinkedIn profile. Social networks have a massive global user base. Profiles often contain very detailed and up-to-date information.

Research & examples: Acquisti & Fong (2015a; 2015b) study to what extent someone's profile on social networks influences their interview invitation rates.

- LinkedIn: most work on LinkedIn covers the platform or the company running it (Caers & Castelyns, 2011; Bonsòn & Bednárová, 2013; Rangel, 2014 and Zide *et al.*, 2014). Only a handful of studies use data obtained from LinkedIn to study different phenomena, such as migration (State *et al.*, 2014; Barslund & Busse, 2016) or job applications (Gee, 2015).
- Facebook: there exist many studies on/using Facebook data (see Wilson *et al.* (2012) for a review), but only a small number of them is dedicated to labour market issues. Issues include recruitment (Bohnert & Ross, 2010; Karl *et al.*, 2010a, 2010b; Kluemper & Rosen, 2009), labour supply (Kelkar & Kulkarni, 2013) and other topics (Gee *et al.*, 2015a; 2015b).
- Twitter: research generally focuses either on the message, the use, the concept or the technology behind Twitter (Williams *et al.*, 2013). Kearney & Levine (2015) use Twitter to study behaviour.

Google Trends

Launched in 2006, Google Trends is a service based on Google Search that enables its users to verify how often search terms, or combinations thereof, are entered relative to the total number of searches performed (by region, across time). When multiple search terms are entered, their relative popularity is compared. Google Trends also shows a list of 'hot searches' and 'hot topics', both of which capture the fastest growing trends on Google Search and in traditional and social media.

Research & examples: Google Trends data are used in a wide range of applications, commonly in the context of behavioural analysis (Rode & Shukla, 2014; Kearney & Levine, 2015 and the work of Stephens-Davidowitz)⁵, forecasting and nowcasting (Choi & Varian, 2012; Chen *et al.*, 2015), other predictions or measurement exercises (Constant & Zimmermann, 2008; Askitas & Zimmermann, 2009; Choi & Varian, 2009).

Web-based surveys

Data on wages, working conditions, employer reviews, and many other labour-related details are collected through web-based surveys. Web-based surveys were among the first types of research conducted online (Kiesler & Sproull, 1986; Kehoe & Pitkow, 1996). Web surveys are fast, flexible, cheap and easy to set up and analyse, and they allow data collection from a large, diverse sample. For the US, there are two interesting web-based panel surveys that are being increasingly used: RAND's American Life Panel and the Understanding America Study Panel. Both are representative for the US adult population.

Research & examples: covers a range of topics, such as employment opportunities (Thiele, 2014), wages and remuneration (Tijdens *et al.*, 2013; Steinmetz *et al.*, 2014; Varkkey *et al.*, 2014; Zofkova & Stroukal, 2014), employer and career branding (Lauby, 2013), working conditions and well-being (Munoz de Bustillo & de Pedraza, 2010; Chandra, 2012); but also topics of a more methodological nature (e.g. de Pedraza *et al.*, 2010; Tijdens, 2014).

⁵ This work can be found here: <http://sethsd.com/>.

- Glassdoor: Glassdoor is a website, hosted on glassdoor.com, which functions as an online job board but also provides other information. More specifically, it allows employers to post vacancies and recruit potential employees through the website. In addition, the website targets job seekers and current employees, who can post their CV, rate their current or former employer and CEO, provide information on their working conditions and wages as well as the recruitment process. Users can interact with current or former employees to ask questions. For employers, Glassdoor provides branding and job advertising solutions. As most of the information on the site comes from former and current employees, it has a clear 'survey' dimension.
- WageIndicator: WageIndicator consists of a series of websites (one for each country), which collect micro data on global labour market trends. Information is collected via online surveys, in which visitors of the WageIndicator websites can participate (i.e. on a voluntary basis). In the survey, respondents are asked about their demographic status, occupation, wage, contributions and other entitlements to social security, working hours and conditions, well-being and job satisfaction, to name just a few topics. WageIndicator is an incredibly rich data sources, as it contains detailed information on minimum and real wages, labour laws and collective agreements, interviews and training advice in a high number of countries and languages.

3.2 What are the strengths and limitations of web-based data?

3.2.1 Strengths

Where traditional data sources, such as (labour force) surveys or census data, and methodologies fall short, an analysis based on web data may be useful to overcome these issues. The first set of benefits relates to the *data collection process* (Wade & Parent, 2001; Benfield & Szlemko, 2006; Kennan *et al.*, 2006; and Mang, 2012). Internet data can be collected in real time. In contrast to traditional sources, there are no lags or revisions. Another advantage is that web data allow researchers to collect large and diverse samples in a fast, flexible, easy and inexpensive way. Web data also make some of the tedious and complicated steps of collecting data from traditional sources redundant (e.g. data entry). Similarly, even though printed vacancies are a rich data source, they are more difficult to manage and manipulate than job advertisements published online.

Secondly, web data can be used to *fill research gaps* (Shapiro, 2014). Internet data are particularly valuable to cover those areas where traditional sources do not exist or are only limited (e.g. low quality or a lot of missing information). In that way, web data can also enable research on topics or concepts that are difficult to grasp or measure with traditional data sources. An important example is self-employment (OECD, 2014). Self-employment is a driver of job creation and entrepreneurship and has, therefore, received much attention from policy-makers. Nonetheless, it is not well-represented in traditional data sources according to Fairlie & Robb (2009). More specifically, the traditional data sources on self-employment commonly only provide details on the business or on the owner, and only few datasets appear to combine both. Other issues are that data are lagged and self-employment is defined in different ways in different sources.

Another advantage is that web data often are publicly available and relatively detailed. Moreover, job advertisements, in particular, typically have a clear structure and contain real job titles, descriptions and requirements (Shapiro, 2014). They have clear space and time dimensions and reflect what is demanded in the labour market. As such, vacancies provide an excellent tool to study new occupations and skills as they arise, which is why they are at the heart of our work – along with other data available on the job boards that publish them.

Besides vacancies and job portals, other web-based data sources may be relevant. One way to detect new occupations is by asking survey respondents to select their occupation from a list of options or find it via a search tree (e.g. the WageIndicator survey). These occupations have an ISCO classification code. When a respondent cannot find his or her occupation, he/she can enter it into the survey. In this case, the occupation may be new or just emerging. A similar procedure can be followed for skills.

3.2.2 Caveats

3.2.2.1 Online job portals and labour market intermediaries

Carnevale *et al.* (2014), Kureková *et al.* (2015) and Kearney & Levine (2015) have drawn attention to the methodological issues related to using data obtained from online job board (vacancies in particular) and intermediaries. Few other studies have discussed the limitations of web data (e.g. Benfield & Szlemko (2006); Shapiro (2014); Beblavý *et al.*, 2016a). The main issue is data representativeness, which takes the following forms:

- incomplete information: not for every job opening a vacancy is published, not all vacancies are published online, and vacancies may not refer to (new) jobs. It is impossible to collect all vacancies, even if all would be published online. Vacancies only represent a small part of labour demand and are, therefore, often combined with other sources (Dorrer *et al.*, 2012; Wright, 2012; Carnevale *et al.*, 2014);
- target specific profiles only: vacancies appear to be targeted towards highly-educated white collar workers and STEM jobs in the US (Carnevale *et al.*, 2014);
- data collection and data processing: data are volatile and may be inconsistent; vacancies may be duplicate and poorly structured; vacancies may not contain all requirements demanded;
- other issues: ethical and technical issues; adverse selection of job applicants (Autor, 2001); vacancies are typically not standardised or stored (Shapiro, 2014; Kureková *et al.*, 2015).

3.2.2.2 Social networks

Despite the fact that web data are generally easier to collect than data from traditional sources, extracting data from social media may prove to be more difficult to obtain when compared with other online sources. Data representativeness is also an issue because social networks may mainly attract certain groups of people:

- Facebook: Wilson *et al.* (2012) note that data crawling is becoming less effective to extract data from Facebook due to stricter privacy settings;
- Twitter: may be difficult to access, and data are limited to the last seven days (see Kwak *et al.*, 2010, for details on how to use crawling techniques). There are no historical data or frequency counts, data come in a format that is hard to manipulate, there is no geographical information;
- interestingly, in recent years social network platforms have reached out to the academic community, through initiatives such as the Twitter Data Grants or the LinkedIn Economic Graph.

3.2.2.3 Google Trends

In their recent influential paper, Kearney & Levine (2015) identify two main concerns when using Google Trends data:

- sample bias: results from the fact that only a sample of searches is fed into the Google Trends analysis;
- searches with too few observations are excluded;
- sampling variability issues: related to the first issue, standard error calculations are problematic when data are treated as fixed instead of random;
- other issues: no data on demographics, potential endogeneity effects which may be hard to control for.

3.2.2.4 Web-based surveys

Data are not representative because participation is voluntary and response rates can be low (Benfield & Szlemko, 2006): information may be missing, some groups of the population may not be targeted (e.g. individuals without Internet access), literacy of participants matters, credibility and authenticity of the answers provided may be questionable, ethical and technical issues etc. Key methodological issues are *sample bias, measurement error, non-response and attrition*.

3.3 How can these web-based data be accessed?

Generally, there are several ways in which data can be accessed from online sources:

- data can be made available on the website of interest or that of a partner (e.g. WageIndicator data). In addition, data can be obtained from the site's structure (labelled 'meta-data' in the remainder of this report);
- data can be collected by private companies and offered for sale or free of charge when used for research (e.g. data from Burning Glass). Such data are typically cleaned and coded, but may be aggregated to ensure anonymity;
- data can be obtained by 'web crawling' or 'web spidering' (see a.o. Capiluppi & Baravalle, 2010; Kuhn & Shen, 2013; Carnevale *et al.*, 2014). This technique is commonly used to extract and process job advertisements. Especially the data processing step can be complicated and is strongly dependent on the content and the structure of the job advertisements collected.

In our work, we have experimented with *data obtained from online job boards and employment websites* in particular. This choice is motivated by our aim to develop and test an innovative method to identify new occupations and skills using Internet data. For this purpose, job portals are an obvious candidate. We acknowledge the potential of other data sources, such as web surveys (e.g. the WageIndicator survey), Google Trends and social networks, but have not exploited these sources so far.

4. Putting these innovative methodologies to the test: identifying new jobs and skills using Internet data

Online job boards can be used in two ways, as was already hinted at above: either one uses the *vacancies and CVs* published, or one relies on the structure of the portal and the *meta-data* that it offers.

4.1 A first approach: vacancies & CVs

Job vacancies and CVs can be assembled via web crawling or ‘spidering’ (Capiluppi & Baravalle, 2010; Kuhn & Shen, 2013; Carnevale *et al.*, 2014). With a ‘spider’ or web bot, a substantial sample of job advertisements can be obtained and stored into a database. The data collection process is relatively easy and fast. Vacancies are typically detailed, and contain crucial information such as a job title, description (e.g. responsibilities, tasks), requirements (e.g. level and type of education, skills) and other information (e.g. details on the position, firm or industry; such as salary, company name and field of activity). By collecting a sample of job advertisements, one can find new job titles and identify new tasks and skills required. These jobs may be completely new or already exist in different countries or sectors. As new occupations arise because new tasks are introduced in the economy (Crosby, 2002), a careful analysis of job vacancies is a good start. A comparison of the skill requirements can shed light on these dynamics. Tijdens *et al.* (2012), however, do point out that linking job titles to an occupational structure is not straightforward, especially when they cover multiple countries and languages.

One of the main difficulties of using vacancy data is that data cleaning, processing and management are relatively complicated (Carnevale *et al.*, 2014). Data are assembled in a database, extracted and parsed into smaller fragments. These fragments are then coded and analysed. This process can be straightforward or very difficult, depending on the structure and the content of the job vacancy. To carry out this process, a comprehensive taxonomy of variables and words is essential. In addition, semantic analysis and text mining are often required to support the coding of the data. These issues are difficult to address, but nonetheless have to be overcome when one uses vacancy or CV data.

4.2 A second approach: meta-data from job portals

Alternatively, one can simply rely on the *meta-data* of the online job portals, rather than the vacancies and CVs published. Job boards are typically structured in such a way that a job seeker is offered a range of similar vacancies (rather than one perfect match) when looking for job offers. This implies that portals arrange their content or advertisements within a clear framework, often based on an occupational classification. Job portals often contain tens of thousands of vacancies, which have to be organised in a structured way in order to keep them manageable.

How does a job board set up an occupational classification? Again, there are several approaches that can be followed. A first approach is to *create an occupational classification on the basis of a system of ‘tags’*. Job advertisements can be assigned to specific categories or ‘tagged’ by the advertiser or the portal. Tags can refer to many things, such as job type, employer type, location, sector, wage bracket, etc. On most, but not all, job portals each vacancy is also assigned one or more occupation tags. Some

job boards publish their list of tags online, so that job seekers can select their occupation of interest from the list. Other portals store the list of tags in a library that can be accessed by an application program interface (API) search. In this case, when job seekers start typing into a search box, the system generates options for automatic completion (as illustrated in Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1 Example of autocomplete functionality from job board *reed.co.uk*. The job tags that appear when one types 'res' are displayed

A second approach is to associate occupations on the basis of keywords that appear in the body of the vacancies that are published. This approach, however, appears to be less reliable. For example, it could occur that a social worker position is offered to a job seeker looking for the keyword 'finance', because the word 'finance' is mentioned in the job advertisement.

One should not think of such an occupational classification as a 'static' list. Instead, in both cases the occupational classification is regularly updated to account for changes in the labour market (e.g. occupations that appear or disappear, new skills that are being requested, etc.). The Slovak job board *profesia.sk* is a good example: between 2011 and 2014, the job board added about 10 new occupations each year. Job portals' occupational classification is a good data source to capture the occupational structure in a region at a certain point in time. These classifications can also be compared with those from other sources, such as ISCO and ESCO, to identify new occupations (e.g. what is available on the job portals but missing in the official lists?).

4.3 Putting both approaches to the test: empirical evidence from a six case studies

Case studies 1 to 3 are based on vacancies, case studies 4 and 5 on meta-data and case study 6 is cross-cutting.

4.3.1 Case study 1: ‘Do educational requirements in vacancies match the educational attainments of job-holders? An analysis of web-based data for 279 occupations in the Czech Republic’

(Tijdens et al., 2015)

The first case study that was carried out in light of the InGRID project deals with skill mismatches in the Czech Republic. The study aimed to address the fact that data on skill mismatches are not necessarily available, unlike what one may expect. Allen et al. (2013) suggest that only very limited data on the skill requirements of employers are available, which, in addition, may not be comparable to the existing measures on skill supply. Given that especially data on skill demand are problematic, we looked into new methods to obtain such data. In the paper, the concept of ‘skills’ overlaps with that of ‘educational attainment’ due to data availability issues. Traditionally, data on skill demand are derived from vacancy monitoring, employer surveys or by asking employees about their current job’s requirements, and to a lesser extent from licensing registers and expert surveys.

We combined data from the WageIndicator Internet survey conducted among Czech job holders with the EURES vacancy data. Data from both sources are aggregated into occupations (i.e. 4-digit ISCO codes) and compared. *WageIndicator* data from the period January 2010 until December 2013 are merged. All visitors of the WageIndicator website are invited to voluntarily complete a survey (which runs continuously). These data are assembled in annual databases. Occupations are coded in ISCO-08, while education is coded in ISCED-97. When WageIndicator data are compared with labour force data from Eurostat, it becomes clear that highly-educated individuals are overrepresented in the survey. The opposite holds for medium- and lower-education individuals.

EURES job vacancy data are composed of the data that the national public employment services supply to the website. The vacancies are coded in ISCO-88 and ISCED-97. Data were collected in December 2013. EURES data for the Czech Republic are fairly complete, as the Czech public employment service requests that all job advertisements are reported to them. These job advertisements are subsequently reported to and published on the EURES website. When compared with the total number of vacancies in Eurostat, the number of vacancies on EURES is very similar for the Czech Republic.

In both datasets, the focus is on *occupations* and *skills*. The skills, captured by ISCED-97 codes for educational attainment in both sets, are already comparable. We distinguish between five education levels, ranging from primary education to higher education. The occupations carry different codes in the EURES and WageIndicator data. In both cases, the categorisation is based on ISCO (the ILO’s occupational classification scheme) but the edition differs. The EURES occupations are, therefore, recoded into ISCO-08, using a conversion table provided by the ILO.

We report a substantial variation in labour supply and demand across the occupations examined. For one-third of the occupations, demand is at least five times the supply. For 25% of the occupations, supply is at least five times larger than demand. Furthermore, there is a negative relationship between the demand for an occupation and the educational requirements listed in the vacancies for this occupation, and a negative relationship between the demand for an occupation and the educational attainments of employees working in the occupation, but this conclusion does not hold for the lowest attainment levels. Another important result is that the level of educational attainments of current employees is larger than what is required in the vacancies.

4.3.2 Case study 2: 'Skills requirements for the 30 most-frequently advertised occupations in the US: An analysis based on online vacancy data'

(Beblary' *et al.*, 2016c)

For our second case study using job advertisements, we relied on data extracted from Burning Glass Technologies. Burning Glass provides job market analytics, applications and data to inform policy-makers, employers, education institutes, recruiters and others about current developments in the labour market. The organisation uses real-time data, extracted from job postings, to this end.

We use data obtained for the 30 most-frequently-advertised occupations in the United States. In total, 1,998,000 vacancies were collected via Burning Glass during the 12-month period September 2013 - August 2014. Using a 12-month period prevents that results are driven by seasonal effects. Burning glass data are particularly interesting as the company aggregates vacancies from about 15,000 online job boards and company sites. These job postings are coded and categorised, which implies that occupation and industry codes are commonly available. Job advertisements generally contain information on education, skills and experience requirements is also provided.

Among the 30 most-frequently advertised occupations, we find cooks, security guards, nurses, managers, cashiers, office clerks, labourers and truck drivers. In other words, our data set contains high- skilled, medium- skilled and low-skilled occupations. Following the classification proposed by Kureková *et al.* (2015b), which is based on ISCO, our sample is composed of 2 low-skilled (ISCO 9), 20 medium-skilled (ISCO 4-8), and 8 high-skilled occupations (ISCO 1-3). In the US, the 5 most-frequently advertised occupations are: retail salesperson (233,851 vacancies), customer service representative (CS) (197,232 vacancies), sales worker supervisor (164,298 vacancies), secretary (114,918 vacancies) and sales representative wholesale (111,177 vacancies). The average number of job advertisements available across the 30 occupations is 66,292.

With this set of vacancies, we examined the requirements that US employers have, by analysing the text of the vacancies, identifying crucial keywords and keeping track of the share of job advertisements –in total and for individual occupations- that refer to these keywords. In particular, we focused on six types of qualifications: *education and formal qualifications*, *cognitive skills*, *non-cognitive skills*, *appearance/look*, *experience* and *other requirements* (e.g. having a clean criminal record, being subject to drug testing and being a US citizen). For each type, we use a set of keywords to identify demand (the keywords are listed in Table 4.1). Combinations and variations of these keywords are also used. When at least one of the keywords was present in the vacancy, it was considered to request the requirement of interest. By taking a broad perspective, we are able to identify the skills that are important in the US and focus on new skills if needed.

In our study, *education and formal qualifications* involve requirements for education, specialised training and licenses. *Cognitive skills* are defined as skills 'typically identified with intelligence and the ability to solve abstract problems' (Kureková *et al.*, 2015b, p. 8) and they can be '*specific*' or '*generic*' in nature. In our work, the specific cognitive skills are: computer skills, analytical skills, language skills, and having a driver's license. Among the generic cognitive skills we include the ability to learn. *Non-cognitive skills* are 'personality traits that are to some extent correlated with intelligence measures' (Brunello & Schlotter, 2011). They have a 'characteristics' and an 'attitude' dimension (Anderson & Ruhs, 2008). Following Kureková *et al.* (2015b) we differentiate between '*social*' and '*personal*' non-cognitive skills. The former consists of communication skills, service skills and team-work skills. The latter contains seven types of skills or personality traits: timeliness, independence, reliability, manners, creativity, flexibility and stress-resistance. In recent years, the roles of cognitive and non-cognitive skills in the education and the labour market outcomes of individuals have been debated. Research shows that non-cognitive skills may be particularly important in service jobs.

67% of the vacancies examined include formal education requirements. 49% of these vacancies demand service skills and 38% of them refer to experience. These three factors constitute the main

filters that US employers use to select job applicants. Interestingly, other non-cognitive skills are also relevant: 30-40% of the vacancies refer to a pleasant demeanour (manners) and flexibility, while 20-30% contain communication skills, timeliness and creativity. As expected, there are huge differences among the 30 occupations. In general, vacancies in the United States prove to be relatively demanding in terms of the requirements that applicants have to meet, and this also applies to low-skilled and mid-skilled jobs. Nevertheless, employers tend to be more demanding as the level of complexity of an occupation goes up (at least for some requirements).

Table 4.1 Overview of the keywords used to identify six types of qualifications

<i>Education & formal qualifications</i>		
	Formal education	Diploma, GED, bachelor, college, university, degree, high school
	Specialised training & licenses	Apprenticeship, training, card, certificate, certification, certified, CDA, ASE, CPR, AED
<i>Cognitive skills</i>		
Specific	Computer skills	Computer, PC, CRM, Microsoft (Office, Word, Excel, Power Point, Outlook, and Access), Windows, SAP
	Analytical skills	Mathematics, analytical, logic, quantitative
	Language skills	Bilingual, English, Spanish, language
	Driver's license	Driver's license
Generic	Ability to learn	Ability to learn, able to learn
<i>Non-cognitive skills</i>		
Social	Communication skills	Communication, speak, write, articulate, verbal, interact, communicate
	Service skills	Client, customer, guest, needs and attention
	Team-work skills	Team, attitude, focus, leader work, environment, spirit
Personal	Creativity	Creative
	Flexibility	Flexible, stay overnight, travel, shifts, work evenings
	Independence	Self-motivated, initiative, independent
	Pleasant demeanour & manners	Attitude, positive, mature, helpful, confident, enthusiastic, professional
	Reliability	Attention to detail, dependable, reliable
	Stress-resistant	Calm, stress, crisis situation
	Timeliness & punctuality	Timely manner, deadlines, act quickly, punctual, prioritise
<i>Experience</i>		
	Experience	Experience combined with year, month, work, preferred, desirable
<i>Appearance/ look</i>		
	Appearance	well-groomed, clean, neat, professional appearance
<i>Other</i>		
	Citizenship	US citizen, citizenship
	Criminal record	No criminal record, clean criminal record
	Drug testing	Drugs, drug testing

4.3.3 Case study 3: 'The IT skills pyramid: A study on the demand for digital skills on the US labour market'

As a follow-up to the first study in which we used Burning Glass data, we prepared a second paper in which we focus specifically on *IT skills*. As a starting point for this work, we consider how technological progress affects the US labour market - building on the vast literature that exists on this topic. For many years, researchers have pointed to *skill-biased technological change* to explain growing inequalities (in terms of employment and/or wages) between skilled and unskilled workers (see a.o. Krueger, 1993; Nickell & Bell, 1996; Mendez, 2002; Oesch & Rodriguez, 2011 and Weiss & Garloff, 2011). Also for the US, research has provided evidence of upskilling and skill gaps. Other work has nuanced these claims, arguing that skill-biased technological change only cannot account for *job polarization* (i.e. when the demand for high-skilled and low-skilled jobs⁶ expands at the expense of that for medium-skilled jobs (Autor *et al.*, 2003; Wright & Dwyer, 2003; Goos & Manning, 2007; Jung & Mercenier, 2014)). This phenomenon has been witnessed in many countries, including the US (Autor *et al.*, 2006). Job polarization can be driven by many factors, with *routinisation-biased technological change* being a major one (Autor *et al.*, 2003). In this scenario, technology can replace labour in routine tasks, which are generally in the middle of the skill distribution but not in non-routine tasks (Goos & Manning, 2007). All these phenomena have important policy consequences. They raise questions such as 'how can society adapt to these transitions' and 'which skills does the labour force need in order to keep up?'

Against this background, our focus is on IT or digital skills and the case of the United States. This focus is motivated by the recent emphasis on the role of the computerisation and the emerging debate on 'digital skill gaps' (see Frey & Osborne, 2013). While basic computer skills are becoming *implicit skills*⁷, and increasingly are considered a prerequisite for most jobs, the computer literacy of the US population seems to lag behind (cf. the results of the PIAAC survey; see OECD, 2013). The education sector is insufficiently prepared to deal with these technological changes and workers enter the labor market lacking the skills they need. The supply of IT skills is well-documented. Despite the debates, still not much is known about the demand for IT skills in the US. Vacancy data can, therefore, provide us with some relevant insights.

Within the study, a distinction is made between three groups of digital skills: basic, intermediate and advanced (following previous work using similar data sources, see the report by Burning Glass Technologies, 2015). This classification suggests a hierarchy between the skills, which is also reflected in the demand for these skills. The data are obtained from Burning Glass and cover the 30 most-frequently advertised occupations. We calculate the share of vacancies in general and by occupation that make reference to certain keywords used to capture the digital skills. For the *basic digital skills*, we consider the keywords computer skills, software, hardware, e-mail, Internet, web, etc. Basic computer skills are requested in about one-third of the vacancies, closely followed by e-mail and Internet (about 20% in both cases). A positive relation is found between the complexity of an occupation and the demand for these skills.

Secondly, *intermediate digital skills* are skills such as word or text processing (including Microsoft Word, Word, etc.), spreadsheets (including MS Excel), MS PowerPoint, office packages (including MS Office, Open Office, etc.) and SAP. These skills are also labelled 'productivity software skills'. 12% to 15% of the vacancies call for text processing and spreadsheets; about 8% explicitly refers to office packages. As before, the demand for intermediate digital skills rises with the complexity of an occupation.

Finally, a set of *advanced digital skills* is considered. This set combines the most complex and diverse skills that we studied. Job applicants who do not possess these skills, would not at all qualify for a

⁶ Especially in the service sector, see Maxwell (2006).

⁷ Interestingly, for the European case, about 550 IT skills are identified by ESCO, which is the European Commission's classification of Education, Skills, Competencies and Occupations. Yet, these IT skills are listed as 'job-specific' skills rather than 'transversal' skills.

position that requires them. We focused on nine classes of skills, each captured with different keywords: CRM (e.g. customer relationship management, etc.), data management and databases (e.g. SQL, MS Access, etc.), data analysis and statistics (e.g. data processing, Stata, Matlab, etc.), programming and programming languages (e.g. C++, Python, JAVA, etc.), digital media and web design (e.g. web development, Photoshop, etc.), desktop publishing (e.g. MS Publish, Visual studio, etc.), CMS (content management system, etc.), social media and blogging (e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn, WordPress, etc.), and SEO (e.g. search engine optimization, etc.). Of these skills, the category databases and data management is the most highly represented in the vacancies (in about 10% of the job advertisements). In addition, the variation across occupations appears to be substantial. As expected, advanced digital skills show up particularly in vacancies for medium- and high-skilled white collar workers and are often only relevant for a few occupations.

4.3.4 Case Study 4: 'An occupations observatory'

(Beblavy *et al.*, 2016d)

For the fourth case study, we opt for a different approach to identify new occupations and skills. This alternative approach is still based on web data and online job boards in particular but, instead of using vacancies, we rely on the structure of the job portal and the tag system that it uses to cluster job advertisements. Online job boards use a tag system to structure the large amount of vacancies that they publish. Tags often refer to specific occupations, but can also cover many other factors (e.g. sector, region, company type, etc.). Generally, from the list of tags that the job portal uses, an occupational classification can be derived. This classification is regularly updated, to account for new occupations and skills and remove redundant ones. This means that the occupational classifications are up-to-date, allowing us to capture new occupations as they arise (in contrast to traditional methods where the classifications used are only rarely updated).

We piloted an innovative approach based on changes in the occupational classification of 11 job portals, with the aim to discover whether this approach could be adopted on a larger scale to identify new occupations and to further our understanding of the skills, education and other requirements that new occupations bring. We selected Belgium, the Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Spain and the United Kingdom for our pilot (the list of portals can be found in Table 4.2). Given that this is a pilot, we did not set out to cover all EU countries. Instead, we selected a sample of job boards in a subset of countries, covering different regions. The 11 countries chosen represent about 75% of the EU population.

For these countries, we were able to find job boards that cover a substantial part of the labour market and that have a tag system, which we verify by checking whether or not the search box has automatic completion or a publicly available list of tags. Other criteria were that the portal is regularly updated and contains at least 3,000 vacancies. In most cases, the list of occupation tags was not publicly available and had to be recovered via web crawling techniques or through querying the website's autocomplete API (i.e. an application programming interface) (from a repository, see for example Figure 4.2).

Table 4.2 List of pilot countries and job boards selected

Belgium	vacature.com (Dutch-speaking part) (www.vacature.com/vacature/bladeren/functienaam/), references.be (French-speaking part) (www.references.be/job/parcourir/fonction/)
Czech Republic	jobs.cz (www.jobs.cz/)
Denmark	jobsnet.dk (https://job.jobnet.dk/CV)
France	keljob.com (www.keljob.com/emploi/metiers)
Germany	jobs.de (www.jobs.de/regional/taetigkeitssuche)
Hungary	profession.hu (www.profession.hu/)
Italy ⁸	lavoro.corriere.it (http://lavoro.corriere.it/)
Poland	jobs.pl (www.jobs.pl/stanowiska-pracy)
Slovakia	profesia.sk (www.profesia.sk/)
Spain	careerbuilder.es (www.careerbuilder.es/)
United Kingdom	jobsite.co.uk (www.jobsite.co.uk/jobs/all/job-titles/)

Figure 4.2 Example of a repository of a job tags from the Danish portal www.jobnet.dk

arbejde", "astronom", "biokemiker", "biolog", "mikrobiolog", "botaniker", "ferskvandsbiolog", "fysiker", "geofysiker", "geolog", "geotekniker", "havbiolog", "hospitalsfysiker", "kemiker", "klimatolog", "levnedsmiddelkandidat", "bromatolog", "levnedsmiddelinspektør", "matematiker", "meteorolog", "miljøtekniker", "molekylærbiolog", "naturgeograf", "statistiker", "zoolog", "organisation, udvikling og rådgivning", "HR-konsulent", "uddannelseskonsulent", "HR-medarbejder", "personalemedarbejder", "personalekonsulent", "researcher, rekruttering", "headhunter", "rådgivende konsulent", "psykologarbejde", "psykolog", "teologisk arbejde", "præst", "sognepræst", "teolog", "undervisning på gymnasier og højskoler", "gymnasielærer, humaniora og kreative fag", "gymnasielærer, naturvidenskab og idræt", "gymnasielærer, samfundsvidenskab", "handelsskolelærer", "højskolelærer", "pædagogisk kandidat", "undervisning på professionshøjskoler", "adjunkt, professionshøjskole", "lektor, professionshøjskole", "underviser, erhvervsakademi", "underviser, professionshøjskole", "seminarielærer", "økonomi og revision", "aktuar", "businesscontroller", "civiløkonom", "erhvervsanalytiker", "erhvervsøkonom", "nationaløkonom /

In order to use this information to identify new occupations, we developed a method that comprises several steps. First, we obtained from each of the 11 job boards the full list of occupation tags. This occupational classification serves as our *benchmark*. It was cleaned for errors such as duplicates or mistakes, and any tags that did not necessarily refer to occupations were removed (e.g. tags referring to locations, sectors, firms or other items). This cleaning process is fully automated, which means that some errors will not be caught. To alleviate this caveat, the benchmark was fully checked manually (by native speakers). Then, the benchmark list of each country was also translated into English, to facilitate cross-country comparisons. Translations were done using the Google Translate website and again verified by native speakers. This is needed, as not all words are always translated properly. In fact, our first results indicate that there were some severe errors in the translations. Moreover, occupations often have a very specific terminology which may not be translated correctly. These issues are particularly important in light of cross-country comparisons.

Secondly, this occupational classification was again obtained at the beginning of each month (i.e. early August, September, etc.) over a six-month period.⁹ We refer to this step as the '*data collection*' step. The occupational classifications extracted are organised in an array and compared to the benchmark. The occupations for which a *match was found* are disregarded. The occupations for which *no match was found in the benchmark* are regarded as potentially new and saved in a database (by country

⁸ The Italian job board had a public list of tags, but this list did not show all the jobs that appeared when the autocomplete function was used. For this reason, the smaller crawled list of jobs was replaced with a more detailed one from autocomplete API.

⁹ At the end of July, we tested our coding. For some countries, this results in an additional list of new occupations for this period.

and date) - in each case creating a shortlist of potentially new occupations. This shortlist again is cleaned (first automatically and then manually) and translated into English via Google Translate, after which another manual check is performed. This data cleaning process is identical to that of the benchmark.

With this procedure, we end up with *two outputs*: the benchmark and the shortlist of potentially new occupations on a specific date (by country). Before the data collection process is started again in the next month, the list of new occupations is added to the benchmark. This prevents occupations from being detected as ‘new’ more than once. The findings from the pilot reveal that for some countries no new occupations were found. There are several possible explanations for this result: for example, it could be that no new occupations emerged or that new occupations emerged but were not picked up by the portal. Alternatively, it could be that potentially new occupations were found but that the manual check of the data revealed that these are not new at all. For instance, on the Belgian job portal an occupation emerged that already exists for decades but for which no vacancies were available before.

Figure 4.3 Illustration of the data collection step

Box 1 An extensive example for the case of Slovakia – data collection step

A new list of occupation tags was obtained from the Slovak job board on 30 July 2015, 6 August 2015, 2 September 2015 and 4 October 2015. Any occupations that were not already part of the benchmark are potentially new, but could also refer to occupations that have been around for years but for which no vacancies were available or for which no separate tags were used. On 30 July, 21 new tags were found, translated into English and compared to the benchmark. Of the 21 occupations, several pointed to potentially new occupations: e.g. drug safety specialist, sound engineer, spa therapist and development specialists switching network. Although one may argue that some of these occupations are common in specific countries, one must keep in mind that occupations have clear space and time dimensions, which implies that these may very well be new on the Slovak labour market. Other occupations were refuted for not being really new: e.g. police officer, soldier and wigmaker. All new tags were added to the benchmark and the data collection process was restarted on August 6. Then, 3 new tags were retrieved: photographer, warder, forest engineer, of which especially the latter could refer to a new occupation. A new list was obtained on September 2 and October 4, both of which resulted in another set of 3 new tags: geologist, revision pharmacist and specialist OSS/BSS and forester, forest technician and head of post. We used our list of candidates that potentially capture new occupations – such as spa therapist, drug safety specialist or OSS/BSS specialist in the above example – for a more in-depth analysis which is explained in further detail below.

Thirdly, there is the ‘*data analysis*’ step. In this step, the shortlist of potentially new occupations - which has been cleaned as explained above and reduced to only those occupations that could be new - is further processed. Occupations that obviously are not new are dropped from the shortlist of new occupations, but they are nevertheless added to the benchmark for future reference. Furthermore, any mistakes that are due to the data collection or matching procedures are taken care of as well. In

Table 4.3, we report the number of tags or occupations in the benchmark, the total number of new tags detected and the number of new tags that actually referred to (potentially) new occupations (i.e. ‘valid’ tags). There is a lot of heterogeneity across job boards, both in terms of the number of tags in the benchmark and the number of new tags. This finding, however, should be interpreted with caution. It does not necessarily imply that new occupations only and/or mostly emerged in a subset of the countries. In fact, the Belgian portal has a very high number of new tags, but these tags generally referred to general concepts rather than new occupations. On 9 March 2016, 42 job advertisements were assigned the tag ‘wood’, covering different occupations such as ‘CNC machine operator in the wood processing industry’ and ‘salesperson of wood products’ on the Belgian portal. Therefore, careful manual inspections of potential new occupation tags are essential to prevent false positives. As is evidenced by Table 4.3 below, only a small percentage of the new tags correspond to potentially new occupations. The remaining tags generally appeared to refer to traditional occupations, which were not advertised online or for which no vacancies were available when the benchmark was created. Another reason might be that some tags are associated with seasonal jobs, which are only advertised during a specific time of the year. More details on the number of tags and the type of tags detected can be found in Appendix A.

Table 4.3 Number of tags in the benchmark and on the shortlist for each country*

Country	Number of tags in benchmark	Number of new tags	Number of valid new tags
BE	415	714	NA
CZ	424	0	0
DE	1,507	0	0
DK	2,163	0	0
ES	233	2	1
FR	1,087	32	11
HU	369	91	11
IT	962	0	0
PL	795	15	7
SK	468	30	16
UK	6,063	0	0

* The number of valid tags for Belgium is missing, because of the peculiar way in which the job portal adds new tags (which, as explained, not only refer to actual occupations but also to other items and words). Therefore, there were many tags that indeed carried valuable information, but a manual inspection of these tags was required to discover which ones captured new or emerging occupations.

In order to discover whether an occupation is indeed new, in a specific sector or the global economy/in the country or elsewhere, an in-depth analysis is carried out. To this end, we create an occupation card for each potentially new occupation. All occupation cards are combined into an occupations observatory. An occupation card has six parts, in which more information on the occupation are provided. By putting all this information together, we verify whether the occupation is indeed new. The first section deals with the identification of the occupation, presenting details on the vacancy that introduced the tag. The second section discuss the responsibilities and tasks associated with the new occupation. In the third section, the requirements and qualifications demanded (e.g. education, skills and experience) are studied. These first sections give some first insights into whether the occupation is completely new or already emerging, new in a specific sector or in the economy as a whole, etc. The fourth section extends the analysis to other countries while the fifth section aims to discover whether the occupation is present in the most recent occupational classifications. The latter is important since the literature defines a new occupation as an occupation that has not yet been

included in the latest occupational classification (Crosby, 2002). The sixth section summarises the card. The template of the occupation cards is presented in Appendix B.

In general, we find that it is feasible to identify new occupations on the basis of this innovative methodology, which relies on meta-data of job boards instead of vacancies, although one can consider a lower frequency (given that new occupations do not emerge very often – as is clear from our case study).

4.3.5 Case Study 5: 'The importance of foreign language skills in the labour markets of Central and Eastern Europe: an assessment based on data from online job portals'

(Beblavý et al., 2016b)

For our second case study based on data derived from online job portals - i.e. their structure and tag system rather than the vacancies - we empirically examine how important knowledge of foreign languages is on labour markets in Central and Eastern Europe. More specifically, we focus on the countries in the Visegrad region: the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia. This case study is motivated by the fact that in a globalised world, knowledge of foreign languages is a very important skill. Especially in Europe, with its 24 official languages and countless regional and minority languages, foreign language skills are a key asset. Yet, while many Europeans are able to speak at least one foreign language, the cross-country variation is considerable (according to the results of the 2012 Eurobarometer).

Our case study is devoted to the Visegrad region, which is relatively open to foreign direct investment and international trade. Because English has developed into the global language of business, knowledge of the language may be relevant skill on the Visegrad labour markets. Furthermore, the Visegrad countries have strong historical, cultural and economic ties with Germany and Austria (making German potentially relevant as well), and have shared a border with the former Soviet Union. In addition, the main national language of none of the four countries is widely spoken in other countries across Europe. While it is not very easy to predict which foreign language skills are the most demanded in the Visegrad region, it is clear that the population's language skills may not be as well-developed as in some other European countries (according to Eurobarometer results).

How do we investigate these research questions? As a first step, we identified for each of the four countries a 'representative' online job portal, which means that these portals were chosen after a thorough analysis of their content and market coverage. For each job board, we assessed their coverage in terms of occupations, sectors, regions, skill levels, etc. In addition to these criteria, job portals also had to use a 'tag system' to organise the vacancies that can be accessed either directly or by search API. With these conditions in mind, the following websites were selected for analysis: www.jobs.cz (Czech Republic), www.profession.hu (Hungary), www.pracuj.pl (Poland) and www.profesia.sk (Slovakia). Only the Slovak job portal publishes a list of tags online (i.e. an overview table presenting all tags and the number of associated job vacancies). To obtain this list for the other job boards, tags were crawled from the autocomplete function of the search box that job seekers use to indicate what type of vacancy they are interested in (i.e. API query). Often, a list of tags corresponds to a list of occupations but, as stated above, many job portals use a range of other tags as well (e.g. related to sector, type of organisation, specific skills, etc.). All lists were collected on 17 July 2015. To rule out that our results are affected by seasonal dynamics, we contacted each of the job boards to inquire about the statistics for the entire year 2015. The Slovak job board informed us that 46% of the vacancies required English, while 14% was tagged 'German'. On the Hungarian portal, 55% of the vacancies demanded English or German, 10% English (specifically) and 2% German. The Czech job board confirmed that 10% of the job advertisements called for German, but the share for English varied between 28% and 59%, depending on whether the job advertisements were supplied by public

employment agencies or employers. We, unfortunately, did not receive any additional information from the Polish job board. Below, we further discuss the results of our initial work.

For each country, we first extracted the total number of vacancies available. This number amounted to 15,269 vacancies on the Czech job board, 11,231 vacancies on the Hungarian job board, 36,079 vacancies on the Polish job board and 11,344 vacancies on the Slovak job board (or about 74,000 advertisements in total across the countries and considering all occupations). Then, we counted how many of these vacancies carried tags referring to foreign language skills.¹⁰ We kept track of the number of job advertisements tagged 'English', 'German', 'Russian', 'French', 'Spanish', etc. and then examined which of these foreign languages was demanded the most (or, in other words, for which tag do we find the highest number of vacancies). In the study, we include the main European languages, languages spoken in the neighbouring countries, languages that may be relevant due to historical, cultural or economic reasons, etc. No distinction is made between reading, writing, listening and speaking skills. One, however, has to be aware that tags are not disjunctive groups: a single job vacancy could request the knowledge of multiple foreign languages.

In the case study, we first look at the total number of vacancies and the share that demands foreign language skills. We then repeat this exercise for a set of occupations for which we can find at least 30 vacancies in all four countries. To perform the occupation-level analysis, occupations had to be matched across the Visegrad countries. To this end, occupation titles had to be translated into English and then compared. Occupations that were not represented in all four countries were dropped from the sample. The remaining occupations were mapped into each other. This was relatively straightforward when there was only one potential match. More commonly, multiple matches were possible. One example is that an individual occupation or tag can be represented by several tags on other job portals. For instance, the tag 'teacher' - which is a single tag in the Czech Republic, Hungary and Slovakia - is divided into two tags, 'teacher' (Nauczyciel) and 'instructor' (Wykladowca), in Poland. Another example is the tag 'programmer', which can be represented by multiple tags (e.g. JAVA, Python and other programmers). When multiple matches were possible, a weighted average was computed (weights equal to the number of vacancies by occupation). As a consequence, in some cases the matching is not 'exact' but instead based on whether or not occupations were 'relatively comparable'. Despite this caveat, the language requirements of the occupations that were mapped into a single occupation are very comparable (considering the share of vacancies that refer to foreign languages). Altogether, 59 occupations were identified in the four countries for which the total number of job advertisements and the number of vacancies that demand foreign languages (i.e. that carry specific foreign language tags) are obtained and used to calculate shares. In the hypothetical example that a job board would contain 500 vacancies for teachers, of which 150 would be tagged 'English', the share would be 0.3. Among the 59 occupations, 2 are low-skilled, 20 are medium-skilled and 35 are high-skilled.

¹⁰ In practice, job seekers can indicate on the website that they are looking for a position where 'English' is a requirement, filtering out jobs for which this is not needed.

Box 3 Illustration for profesia.sk on how to obtain the number of available vacancies in general and by occupation, and the percentage of those that request language skills

On 14 January 2016, there were 10,914 vacancies on www.profesia.sk (blue square on top of the page, Figure 4.4). Of these vacancies, 5,386 demand English (49%) and 1,564 require German (14%). Other criteria that one can select to filter occupations are region and sector (red squares – left side of the page, Figure 4.4). This exercise can also be done for individual occupations (labelled 'positions' on the site). First, one has to select an occupation for the list of positions. In the example in Figure 4.5, we selected 'accountant'. On www.profesia.sk, we found 471 vacancies for accountants (indicated by the blue square on top of the page in Figure 4.5, where we are looking at vacancies 1-20 of this list). Again, we have the option to use other filters, such as sector, company or language skills. In terms of foreign language skills, we see that of the 471 job advertisements for accountants, 372 demand English (79%) and 81 require German (17%) (red square - left side).

Our findings suggest that one-third to three-fourths of the vacancies studied demands foreign language skills. English is the most frequently requested foreign language in the Visegrad group. 52% of the job advertisements calls for English language skills but less than one-third of the population is able to have a conversation in the language (according to the 2012 Eurobarometer). The demand for English is higher for occupations that are more complex than for those that are less complex. German, which is found in 12% of the vacancies, is the second-most-in-demand foreign language in the Visegrad region. Interestingly, the 2012 Eurobarometer results reveal that between 15% and 22% of the Visegrad population has sufficient German language skills to hold a conversation in the language. For German, there is no link between the demand for language skills and the complexity of an occupation. Other languages, such as French, Italian, Spanish and Russian, are only requested in a small minority of the vacancies.

Figure 4.4 Illustration of how to derive the total number of vacancies and the number of vacancies that request specific language skills using the Slovak job board www.profesia.sk. The total number of vacancies is indicated by the blue square (on top of the web page – 10914 jobs), the red squares indicate all selection criteria that can be used to filter vacancies (region, position, contract type, sector, company, language skills and publication time) (on the left side of the web page)

The screenshot displays the search results page on the Slovak job board. At the top, a search bar and a navigation menu are visible. The total number of jobs is shown as 'Jobs 10 914 jobs' in a blue box. On the left side, there are several filter categories, each with a red box around its header: 'REGIONS', 'POSITION', 'CONTRACT TYPE', 'SECTOR', 'JOBS FROM THE COMPANY', 'LANGUAGE SKILLS', and 'JOBS OVER'. Each filter category lists various options with corresponding counts. The main content area shows a list of 'CURRENT JOBS' with a sub-header '1 - 20 of 10 914'. The first job listing is for a 'Technik zberu dát' (Data collection technician) at 'Stredoslovenská energetika - Distribúcia, a.s.' in Žilina. Other job listings include 'Poštový bankár - Sereď, hlavný pracovný pomer (PB PARTNER, a.s.)', 'Konštruktér' (Designer), 'Perfektná príležitosť pre mzdových účtovníkov', 'Komplexný účtovník/účtovníčka s AJ', 'Poštový bankár - Rajec nad Rajčankou', 'Predavačka / Pokladnička', 'Zamestnanec/zamestnankyňa čerstvých potravín', 'Aplikačný architekt pre oblasť BI a reporting', and 'Prívyrob s!!! Expedícia a triedenie /pre každého/'. Each job listing includes a 'Save this job offer' button and a 'today' timestamp. On the right side, there is a 'HOT JOBS' section with a yellow header, listing various job opportunities.

Figure 4.5 Illustration of how to derive the number of vacancies for a specific occupation and the share of vacancies that request specific language skills from www.profesia.sk. The orange square indicates the occupation of interest (accountant), the blue square shows the number of vacancies available for this occupation (right side, top of page), i.e. 471, and the red square indicates the number of available vacancies that also request certain language skills (left side, bottom of page) (372 out of the 471 accountant positions demand English, 81 out of the 471 require German etc.)

The screenshot shows the search results for 'Jobs: accountant' on the website. The search bar at the top left contains 'Searched term' and a search icon. Below it, there is an 'Advanced search' section and a 'Selected criteria' section showing 'Accountant' with a close button. The left sidebar contains several filter categories:

- REGIONS**: Bratislava region (339), Nitra region (36), Trnava region (27), Trenčín region (22), Košice region (16), Žilina region (11), Prešov region (10), Banská Bystrica region (9). Includes options for 'List of locations' and 'Abroad'.
- CONTRACT TYPE**: full-time (458), part-time (24), trade licence (23), agreement-based (Temporary jobs) (18), internship, work experience (3).
- JOBS FROM THE COMPANY**: TOP clients (273), Recruitment Agencies (237), Employers (234). Includes 'List of companies'.
- LANGUAGE SKILLS** (highlighted with a red square): English (372), German (81), Slovak (22), French (14). Includes 'List of language skills'.
- JOBS OVER**: (dropdown menu).

The main content area shows a list of jobs for 'accountant' (highlighted with an orange square). The top right of this section shows '1 - 20 of 471' (highlighted with a blue square). The job listings include:

- Komplexný účtovník/účtovníčka s AJ (Ref. č.: 1-11-22499/PF)** by Grafton Recruitment Slovakia, s.r.o. Bratislava. Includes a 'Save this job offer' button and 'today' status.
- Accountant** by Datavard s. r. o. Vajnorská 100, Bratislava. Includes a 'Save this job offer' button and 'today' status.
- Účtovník s maďarským jazykom** by Deutsche Post DHL DHL Express (Czech Republic) s.r.o. Includes a 'Save this job offer' button and 'today' status.
- Referent účtovného oddelenia/čiastkový účtovník** by Dallmayr Vending & Office k. s. Prístavná 10, 821 09 Bratislava. Includes a 'Save this job offer' button and 'today' status.
- Accountant Clerk - OTC Pricing AE** by JOHNSON CONTROLS INTERNATIONAL spol. s r.o. Bratislava. Includes a 'Save this job offer' button and 'today' status.
- Špecialista účtovníctva** by HANON SYSTEMS SLOVAKIA S.R.O. Ilava. Includes a 'Save this job offer' button and 'today' status.
- Accounts Receivables Management - Cash collection mit Deutschen Sprachkenntnissen (m/w)** by Henkel Slovensko, spol. s r.o. Bratislava. Includes a 'Save this job offer' button and 'today' status.
- Účtovník/čka** by Hella Slovakia Front-Lighting s.r.o. Kočovce pri Novom Meste nad Váhom (4 km) ... Includes a 'Save this job offer' button and 'today' status.
- Junior Pavroll Accountant**

4.3.6 Case study 6: 'Cross-cutting work on non-cognitive skills'

As a final case study, we focus on the identification of *non-cognitive skills (or soft skills)*. This case study is cross-cutting, as it combines insights from a series of research papers that use vacancy data and other information obtained from online sources. Throughout our work, we focus on cognitive as well as non-cognitive skills, arguing that both could be important determinants of social and economic outcomes (e.g. educational attainment or earnings). In the field of economics, the academic literature on non-cognitive skills is fairly recent. The literature started to advance towards the end of the 1990s, fuelled by several seminal contributions from James Heckman. Before that time, academic studies were mainly concerned with *cognitive skills*, and how they affect labour market and social outcomes. In other disciplines, such as psychology and sociology, research into non-cognitive skills is much more developed.

Non-cognitive skills are typically understood as personality traits, which are relevant for human capital outcomes (next to intelligence and cognitive abilities) (Heckman & Rubinstein, 2001; Thiel & Thomsen, 2013). Examples are self-discipline, trustworthiness and tenacity. Similarly, Kautz *et al.* (2014) describe non-cognitive skills as 'attributes that cannot be measured by IQ or achievement test' (p.13). In psychology, personality traits are classified into five groups (also known as the 'Big Five' or under the acronym 'OCEAN'): openness to experiences, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism.

Recent research confirms that non-cognitive skills influence labour market, social and other outcomes. Heckman (1999), for example, finds that a one-side focus on cognitive skills overlooks the fact that non-cognitive skills crucially determine success in later life. Heckman *et al.* (2006) conclude that non-cognitive skills increase wages directly and indirectly, by their impact on productivity and through schooling and work experience. Lindqvist & Vestman (2011) analyse the impact of cognitive and non-cognitive skills on the labour market outcomes in the Swedish army. For men with poor labour market outcomes, i.e. unemployed or low earnings, a lack of non-cognitive skills appears to be the main driver.

Despite this recent upsurge of studies, little is known about the role of non-cognitive skills in the labour market. Heckman & Rubinstein (2001) argue that researchers neglect non-cognitive skills mostly due to *data availability and measurement issues*. While there exist several methods to capture cognitive abilities, it is much more difficult to measure concepts related to personality or motivation (e.g. persistence, trustworthiness, etc.), and often these concepts are lumped together (Heckman & Rubinstein, 2001). In their recent paper, Thiel & Thomsen (2013) conclude that the commonly used measures for non-cognitive skills are ambiguous and often do not manage to strike a good balance between being too broad and too specific. There is also a longstanding debate on whether non-cognitive skills are stable. Kautz *et al.* (2014) show that such skills are stable at any age but can change across the life cycle.

In our work, we aspire to contribute to this literature by capturing non-cognitive skills on the basis of web data (including vacancies, meta-data from the job portals and other information sources). We distinguish between two sets of non-cognitive skills: *personal skills and social skills* (Kureková *et al.*, 2015b). The former captures personal traits that determine how one approaches a task, including reliability, timeliness, independence, creativity, flexibility, manners, and stress-resistance. The latter captures personal traits that determine how one interacts and communicates with others. This set of skills comprises communication skills, team-working skills and service skills.

In our study, we set out to discover how frequently personal and social non-cognitive skills are demanded by employers in Europe and the US on the basis of vacancies (via semantic analysis) and other data sources (e.g. our strategy to identify new occupations could also be used to find tags that refer to non-cognitive skills). As explained in other sections of this report, we mainly analyse the demand for non-cognitive skills on the basis of job postings. More specifically, we prepared a list of keywords that refer to non-cognitive skills (one list for each case study, which overlap to a large extent) and then compare the list with the text of each vacancy. Examples of keywords that were

used are: client, customer, needs and attention (service skills), team, attitude, environment (team-working skills), flexible, stay overnight, travel, shifts (flexibility) and clams, stress, crisis situation (stress-resistant) (see Table 4.1 for other examples). Alternatively, one can identify non-cognitive skills on the basis of the tag system that job boards use to organise their advertisements. We did not explore this approach any further. Our work corroborates earlier studies that did similar analyses, such as Brunello & Schlotter (2011).

4.4 A comparison of the two approaches: advantages and limitations

Both approaches to identify new jobs and skills have their advantages and limitations. A brief overview of these advantages and limitations is presented in the table below.

Table 4.4 Overview of the advantages and limitations of using vacancies and job portal meta-data to identify new occupations and skills

	Vacancies	Meta-data
+	Detailed information, clear structure (job title, job description, requirements, etc.), easy to collect large and diverse sample	Easy and fast to collect, manage, process and analyse data due to smaller samples, and to use and interpret
-	Data processing, coding and analysis is complicated and may be challenging	Depending on the job board, data may not be very detailed or complete, more limited potential for research

5. Conclusions

On the basis of six case studies, we demonstrate that online data, and data extracted from *online vacancies* and *job boards* in particular, are valuable in the analysis of (new) occupations and skills, and the impact of technological progress on the labour market. Web data have become more widely used for labour market research in the last decade, but only few contributions have specifically focused on the topic of new occupations and skills. Nevertheless, this is a key topic for policy-makers, who aim to tackle issues such as skill mismatch and unemployment. Research suggests that traditional methodologies and data sources fall short to identify new occupations and skills. Web data, however, can overcome many of the issues associated with them (e.g. real time data availability). As this research field is now rapidly advancing, we decided to assess some of these new data sources and methods.

To this end, we carried out a number of case studies. *Three of the case studies* are based on a sample of job advertisements published online, such as Burning Glass and other job sites. By keeping track of vacancies, one can study the jobs that arise, the qualifications that they require, and many other details. This allows researchers to use vacancies to identify new occupations and skills. With this methodology, we examined to what extent there are skill mismatches in the Czech Republic, what US employers expect from job applicants for the 30 most-frequently advertised occupations and how important IT skills are on the US labour market. *Two case studies* instead rely on meta-data, i.e. the occupational structure and the tag system that job portals use to cluster their vacancies. By keeping track of the tags that are added or disappear, one can understand what occupations and skills are demanded. We tested this methodology to detect new occupations in an ‘occupations observatory’ and the role of foreign language skills on Central and Eastern European labour markets. The final case study concentrates on non-cognitive skills and is cross-cutting, as such skills can be examined on the basis of job advertisements as well as meta-data.

In this report, we provide evidence for the potential of web data as a source for labour market analysis. Our research focused on occupations and skills in particular and demonstrated that innovative methods are an important step forward in this field.

appendix 1

a1.1 Appendix A: Overview of new occupation tags identified

Table a1.1 List of potentially new occupations: 57 occupations were identified

Country	Occupation	Translated
France	Agent de sécurité incendie	Fire safety officer
France	Formateur logiciel	Software trainer
France	Ingénieur commercial aéronautique	Aviation sales engineer
France	Ingénieur traitement image	Image processing engineer
France	Technico commercial informatique	IT technical sales
France	Agent technico commercial	Technical sales agent
France	Technicien acoustique	Sound technician
France	Technicien support système	System support technician
France	Ingénieur commercial assurance	Insurance sales engineer
France	Agent de sûreté	Security officer
France	Ingénieur acoustique	Sound engineer
Belgium	software ontwikkelaar	Software developer
Belgium	commercieel technisch adviseur (b3182)	Commercial technical advisor (b3182)
Belgium	product manager	Product manager
Belgium	storingstechnieker (m/v)	Failure technician (m/f)
Belgium	technicus beveiliging regio antwerpen	Security technician region Antwerp
Belgium	business development manager (m/v)	Business development manager (m/f)
Belgium	customer technical support & quality specialist	Customer technical support & quality specialist
Belgium	chemical sales	Chemical sales
Belgium	technical designer	Technical designer
Belgium	Ultrasound	Ultrasound
Belgium	automation engineer - vaste job	Automation engineer – fixed position
Belgium	Embedded	Embedded
Belgium	software engineer	Software engineer
Slovakia	Choreograf	Choreographer
Slovakia	Ortopedický technik	Orthopedic technician
Slovakia	Zvukár	Sound engineer
Slovakia	Drug Safety Specialist	Drug safety specialist
Slovakia	Špecialista optimalizácie rádiovkej siete	Specialist radio network optimisation
Slovakia	Špecialista vývoja programov zdravia	Development specialist health programmes
Slovakia	Špecialista plánovania rádiovkej siete	Radio network planning specialist
Slovakia	Špecialista rozvoja spojovacej siete	Development specialist switching network
Slovakia	Klinický psychológ	Clinical psychology

Country	Occupation	Translated
Slovakia	Spa terapeuta	Spa therapist
Slovakia	Lesný inžinier	Forest engineer
Slovakia	Geológ	Geologist
Slovakia	Revízný farmaceut	Revision pharmacist
Slovakia	Špecialista OSS/BSS	Specialist OSS/BSS
Slovakia	Lesný technik	Forest technician
Spain	Refractory engineer	Refractory engineer
Poland	Animator Kultury	Cultural animator
Poland	Kierownik ds. Operacji Dokumentowych	Manager. Documentary operations
Poland	Inżynier ds. Testów	Engineer. Testing
Poland	Inżynier Biomedyczny	Biomedical engineer
Poland	Inżynier ds. Ciągłego Doskonalenia	Engineer. Continuous improvement
Poland	Inżynier Procesu	Process engineer
Poland	Opiekunka Środowiskowa	Environmental supervisor
Poland	Inżynier Biomedyczny	Biomedical engineer
Hungary	Nyomdász	Typographer
Hungary	Terméktervező	Product designer
Hungary	Gyógyypedagógus	Special education teacher
Hungary	Telemarketinges	Telemarketing
Hungary	Gyártómérnök	Manufacturing engineer
Hungary	Dekoratór	Decorator
Hungary	telekommunikációs szakértő	Telecommunications expert
Hungary	Webdesigner	Web designer
Hungary	szoftver tesztmérnök	Software test engineer
Hungary	data analyst	Data analyst
Hungary	Kertészmérnök	Horticulturist

Figure a1.1 displays the number of tags detected over time in all countries, where new occupation tags were detected except for Belgium, which was left out due to a huge number of occupation tags detected every month. Most vacancies were detected in the first month. The reason is that the lists of tags often contain only those tags, which are currently used for at least one vacancy.

Figure a1.1 Number of new occupation tags detected across time (all countries except Belgium)

a1.2 Appendix B: Template of an occupation card

New occupation title

Date: when picked up by the algorithm

A. Identification

In the beginning of *Month X Year X*, a new tag was added to the online job board of *Country X*. This tag was picked up (either via the API or using a web crawling technique that extracts the list of tags) and stored in a database. As a next step, we search for a vacancy for *new occupation X* on the job portal – to discover what triggered the new tag. More details on this tag and vacancy can be found below; these details cover (i) the portal to which the tag was added and where the vacancy was found, and (ii) the content of the sample vacancy that we study in more depth (to identify tasks and responsibilities – skills and other requirements).

Details on the tag and the job advertisement	
When did the tag/vacancy appear online?	
On which online job board was the tag/vacancy published?	
Which country is covered by this job portal?	
In which industry is the employer active?	
What type of employer has posted the vacancy?	

Sample job advertisement	
Job description (responsibilities and tasks of the job) Job profile (education, skills and other requirements for the job) Job portal tags (tags attached to the vacancy on the job board)	

B. Definition, responsibilities and tasks

1. Definition

What is 'new occupation X'?

Is this position related to any existing occupations?

How prevalent is new occupation X in Country X?

2. What are the responsibilities and tasks of new occupation X?

This information is obtained from a sample of job vacancies, extracted from job portals (for Country X)

C. Education, skills and other requirements

This information is obtained from a sample of job vacancies, extracted from job portals (for Country X)

Formal education required	
Is formal education required? Level of education Field of education	

Skills required	
Communication skills Computer skills Non-cognitive skills Occupation-specific skills	

Experience required	
Is experience required? Is job-related experience required?	

D. Geographical prevalence

1. A European perspective

Results from job portals and Google search for countries in different parts of Europe:

Some of the job portals consulted: Indeed, Monster, Stepstone, ...

Similar vacancies in Western Europe	
<p>Western Europe Country 1 Western Europe Country 2 Etc.</p> <p>Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Country X?</p>	<p><u>Tasks/Responsibilities:</u></p> <p><u>Requirements:</u></p>

Similar vacancies in Southern Europe	
<p>Southern Europe Country 1 Southern Europe Country 2 Etc.</p> <p>Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Country X?</p>	<p><u>Tasks/Responsibilities:</u></p> <p><u>Requirements:</u></p>

Similar vacancies in Northern Europe	
<p>Northern Europe Country 1 Northern Europe Country 2</p> <p>Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Country X?</p>	<p><u>Tasks/Responsibilities:</u></p> <p><u>Requirements:</u></p>

Similar vacancies in Central and Eastern Europe	
<p>Central and Eastern Europe Country 1 Central and Eastern Europe Country 1 Etc.</p> <p>Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as the vacancies for Country X?</p>	<p><u>Tasks/Responsibilities:</u></p> <p><u>Requirements:</u></p>

2. A global perspective

Results from **job portals** and **Google search** for countries in different parts of the world
Some of the job portals consulted: Indeed, Monster, Stepstone, ...

Do these vacancies involve similar tasks and have similar requirements as vacancies for Country X?

- Tasks/Responsibilities:
- Requirements:

3. A Google Trends Analysis

E. Occupational classification

1. International classifications

ISCO-08: New occupation X found or not?

Where could this occupation fit in the ISCO08 classification?

ESCO: New occupation X found or not?

Where could this occupation fit in the ESCO classification?

2. National classifications

Country X:

In Europe:

In the rest of the world:

F. Conclusions

Is New occupation X a new or emerging occupation?	
In Country X?	
In Europe?	
Worldwide?	

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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